

Sahil Çamı Kolofanının Fotokopi Kağıdı Üretiminde Kullanımı

Ahmet TUTUŞ¹, Zehra ODABAŞ SERİN¹, Ayşe ÖZDEMİR¹ ve Mustafa ÇİÇEKLER¹

¹ Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi, Orman Fakültesi, Orman Endüstri Mühendisliği Bölümü, 46040, Kahramanmaraş, TÜRKİYE

Sorumlu Yazar: Mustafa Çiçekler, mcicekler87@gmail.com

Özet

Kağıt üretiminde sizing (yapıştırma) işlemi, genel olarak kağıdın suya karşı direncini, fiziksel özelliklerini, mürekkep emilim performansını ve kağıdın yüzey özelliklerini iyileştirmek için uygulanmaktadır. Sizing işleminde kolofan genel olarak ıslak kısımda bünyeden, kuru kısımda ise yüzeyden verilmektedir.

Bu çalışmada, sahil çamından elde edilen kolofanın fotokopi kağıdı üretiminde ıslak kısımda bünyeden, kuru kısımda ise yüzeyden verilerek kağıt özellikleri üzerine etkileri araştırılmıştır. Fotokopi kağıdı üretiminde kolofan hem bünyeden hem de yüzeyden 3 nolu rod ile ayrı ayrı uygulanmış ve sektörde yaygın olarak kullanılan ticari reçine Topsize RD44 ile karşılaştırması yapılmıştır.

Sonuç olarak, yüzey yapıştırmada sahil çamından elde edilen kolofanın Topsize RD44' e göre kağıdın fiziksel özelliklerini daha çok arttırdığı, mürekkep emilim performansını ve kağıdın yüzey özelliklerini iyileştirdiği ve optik özellikleri ise olumsuz etkilediği tespit edilmiştir. Kağıdın suya karşı direnç (Cobb) özellikleri üzerine yüzey yapıştırmada kolofanın, iç yapıştırma ise ticari reçinenin (Topsize RD44) kullanılması en iyi etkiyi göstermiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sahil çamı, kolofan, fotokopi kağıdı, sizing, reçine

Evaluation of Maritime Pine Rosin in Photocopy Paper Production

Ahmet TUTUŞ¹, Zehra ODABAŞ SERİN¹, Ayşe ÖZDEMİR¹ and Mustafa ÇİÇEKLER¹

¹ Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University, Faculty of Forestry, Department of Forest Industry Engineering, 46040, Kahramanmaraş, TURKEY

Corresponding Author: Mustafa Çiçekler, mcicekler87@gmail.com

Abstract

Sizing process in paper production is generally applied to improve water resistance, physical properties, ink absorption performance and surface properties of the paper. The colophony (natural rosin) is generally given in pulp preparation unit and at size press section in the sizing process.

In this study, the effects of the rosin obtained from maritime pine on the photocopy paper properties were investigated. Rosin was used in paper structure and coated to paper surface. It was applied to pulp directly and coated to paper surface with 3rd rod. Papers produced with natural rosin were compared with Topsize RD44, a commercial resin widely used in the sector.

As a result, when compared with the commercial rosin (Topsize RD44), it has been determined that rosin obtained from maritime pine improved the physical properties, ink absorption performance and surface properties of the papers and decreased the optical

properties. Topsize RD44 used in pulp preparation unit and natural rosin used at size press gave the best result in terms of water resistance of the papers (Cobb).

Keywords: Maritime pine, photocopy paper, sizing, colophony, rosin

1. INTRODUCTION

The papers have different properties in terms of surface properties and production methods. In some papers, the amount of cellulose is high, while some papers are surface treated or filled with fillers. All these differences result in a lot of paper types and these types are also classified among them [1]. First grade photocopy papers with 60-80 grammages are sized paper that can be written and printable. It contains chemical cellulose or chemical cellulose and mechanical wood pulp. These celluloses or pulps are subjected to bleaching process and made ready for photocopy paper production. In addition, these papers are subjected to a coating process depending on the usage area [2].

Sizing process in paper production; is made to prevent from penetrating water and other liquids into the paper and board by imparting hydrophobic properties to the fibers. This process reduces the water absorption properties of fibers used in the paper production. Absorbency is not desired in some papers such as corrugated board, photocopy papers, vegetable and fruit packages, envelopes and packaging papers. Sizing process reduces water, moisture and liquid absorption of the papers by giving resins to the paper structure or applying the surface of papers [3]-[5].

Resin is used to provide internal sizing. Filling the gap between the fibers and passing through the drying cylinders, the melt resin spreads as a layer preventing the absorption of water and dyes. There are many commercial resins used in paper production. Resin is a substance consisting of colophony and turpentine. Colophony and turpentine have many usage area in industry. However, colophony, also called rosin is used in the paper sizing process. The alum is added to precipitate the colophony on the fibers [6],[7].

The fast growing foreign species planted in Turkey is Maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster*) which has the widest area in forest trees. As a result of the studies, it is seen that the maritime pine is the preferred species for industrial plantations to be applied in our country. This type, which has high resin content, is used in the production of resins in our country. Besides, many projects are being carried out on the resin production from maritime pine [8],[9].

In this study, the effects of the rosin obtained from maritime pine on the photocopy paper properties were investigated. Rosin was used in pulp preparation unit and at size press section. It was applied to pulp directly and coated to paper surface with 3rd rod. Papers produced with natural rosin were compared with Topsize RD44, a commercial resin widely used in the sector.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Colophony (Rosin) Production

The oleoresin used in the study was obtained from the maritime pine trees in Kocaeli-Kefken region with using acid paste method. Separation of turpentine and colophony (rosin) was carried out with hydro distillation method using Clevenger for 4 hours. Rosin obtained with this method was stored at 4 °C.

2.2. Rosin Application

The rosin application process was carried out in two different ways: to paper structure in wet-end and to the paper surface in dry-end. It was also compared with the rosin used in the market named Topsize RD44. The addition of alum was carried out for the rosin precipitation.

3%, 6% and 9% rosins were applied to paper structure with magnetic stirrer in a beaker. The pH of the suspension was adjusted at 4.5-5.0 with alum during mixing. The pulp and rosin were mixed for homogeneity about 10 minutes. Then, the papers with 80 grammages were produced using Rapid Kothen-paper machine. Rosins dissolved in toluene with 5%, 10% and 15% concentrations were coated to paper surfaces with 3rd screwed coating rod.

2.3. Paper Production

The bleached short (70%) and long (30%) fibers were beaten in the hollander beater to 45±5 °SR (Schopper Riegler) freeness levels according to Tappi T 200 sp-96 and ten handsheets per tested sequence with grammages of 80 gr.m⁻² were prepared using a Rapid-Kothen sheet former according to ISO 5269/2.

2.4. Determination of Physical and Optical Properties

Rosin applied papers kept in the conditioning room for 24 hours were subjected to physical and optical properties in accordance with the standards given in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Standards of the physical and optical tests

Physical and Optical Tests	Standards
Breaking length	TAPPI T494 om-01
Burst index	TAPPI T403 om-15
Cobb ₆₀	TAPPI T441 om-13
Brightness	ISO 2469:2014
Whiteness	ISO 2469:2014
Yellowness	ASTM E313
Opacity	TAPPI T519 om-02

Three replicates were done for each experiment, and mean values were used to determine the physical and optical properties of the papers. The Cobb tests were performed for 60 seconds.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Effects of Rosin on the Physical and Optical Properties of the Photocopy Papers

The physical properties of the rosin applied papers were summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. The physical properties of rosin applied papers

Rosin rates (%)	Breaking Length (km)	Burst Index (kPa.m ² /g)	Cobb ₆₀ (g/m ²)
0	5.96	4.47	197
Natural Rosin (Maritime pine)			
3	4.73	3.78	121
6	5.16	3.70	127
9	5.32	3.65	73
Commercial Rosin (Topsize RD44)			
3	5.10	3.69	35
6	4.83	3.94	18
9	4.60	3.69	17

The results in Table 2 indicated that the breaking length and burst index decreased when rosin applied on the paper structure in certain rates. However, the Cobb₆₀ values have been affected positively with using rosin.

Figure 1. Effects of the maritime pine rosin applied papers on the physical properties

It has been determined that significant reduction in the breaking length has been observed with the addition of natural rosin to the paper structure (Fig. 1). However, as the rosin ratio increased, the breaking length values also increased. Besides, the use of rosin reduced the burst index. The breaking length and burst index decreased about 15.6% and 18.3%, respectively. Due to rosin-water relation, fiber/fiber bonds number were decreased in paper structure. Decreases in fiber/fiber bond numbers which is important for the physical properties, the strength properties of the paper also decrease [5], [7], [10].

Cobb test determines the amount of water absorbed by paper, paperboard, and corrugated fiberboard in a specified time and it is important parameter for internal and surface sizing. As this value decreases, the resistance of the paper to liquids increases [5], [7], [11]. According to Fig.1, the Cobb values of the rosin applied papers decreased significantly. Because of its water-repellent properties and filling of gaps between the fibers, the use of rosin made the

paper more resistant to liquid [12]. The Cobb₆₀ value decreased about 62.9% with using natural rosin in paper structure.

Figure 2. Effects of the commercial rosin (Topsize RD44) applied papers on the physical properties

The use of commercial rosin which has the same effect as natural rosin had adversely affected the physical properties of papers (Fig. 2). However, Topsize RD44 has been very effective in terms of Cobb value compared to natural resin. With using this rosin, the Cobb value decreased about 91.4%. Tutus et al., (2014) reported that Topsize RD44 has significantly reduced the Cobb values of the imitation kraft papers when compared with other commercial rosins [7].

The physical properties of the rosin coated papers were given in Table 3.

Table 3. The physical properties of rosin coated papers

Rosin rates (%)	Breaking Length (km)	Burst Index (kPa.m ² /g)	Cobb ₆₀ (g/m ²)
0	5.96	4.47	197
Natural Rosin (Maritime pine)			
5	5.86	3.46	165
10	6.86	4.66	26
15	8.01	5.64	23
Commercial Rosin (Topsize RD44)			
5	5.70	3.97	115
10	6.20	4.15	119
15	6.30	4.39	124

According to Table 3, coating of the rosins on the paper surface has a positive effect on the physical properties. Particularly the natural rosin has been very effective on tensile and burst strengths. Using maritime pine rosin in surface sizing of photocopy papers increased the breaking length and burst index about 34.4% and 26.2%, respectively. On the contrary, Topsize RD44 was less effective in the physical properties and even it has been reduced burst strength of the papers.

Figure 3. Effects of the maritime pine rosin coated papers on the physical properties

The Cobb values were significantly decreased with using maritime pine rosin (Fig. 3) and have been reduced by approximately 88.3% with coating 15% rosin on the photocopy paper surface.

Figure 4. Effects of the Topsize RD44 rosin coated papers on the physical properties

Topsize RD44 reduced Cobb values to a certain level, even though it is not as high as natural resin. (Fig. 4). The Cobb values have been decreased by approximately 44.6% with coating 5% Topsize RD44 on the photocopy paper surface.

The optical properties of the resin applied and coated photocopy papers were given in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4. The optical properties of rosin applied papers

Rosin rates (%)	Brightness (ISO)	Whiteness (ISO)	Yellowness (E313)
0	77.26	75.23	3.42
Natural Rosin (Maritime pine)			
3	76.66	74.64	3.38
6	77.23	75.10	3.54
9	76.60	74.37	3.72
Commercial Rosin (Topsize RD44)			
3	77.00	74.76	3.74
6	76.55	74.46	3.48
9	76.27	74.19	3.48

Table 5. The optical properties of rosin coated papers

Rosin rates (%)	Brightness (ISO)	Whiteness (ISO)	Yellowness (E313)
0	77.26	75.23	3.42
Natural Rosin (Maritime pine)			
5	75.82	73.32	4.31
10	75.22	72.41	4.73
15	74.07	71.30	4.94
Commercial Rosin (Topsize RD44)			
5	78.01	76.24	2.88
10	77.89	76.08	3.00
15	78.20	76.48	2.81

As seen in the tables, the application of commercial and natural rosins has not been significant effects on the optical properties of photocopy papers. Decrease in the optical properties of the natural rosin applied photocopy papers was not found significant. Besides, increases in the optical properties of the commercial rosin applied photocopy papers was not also found significant. These minor increases and decreases are due to the white and yellowish colors of the rosins.

4. CONCLUSION

1. Commercial rosin gave better Cobb results than natural resin when used in the paper structure. On the contrary, maritime pine rosin has been reduced the Cobb values more than Topsize RD44 in coating process.
2. Rosin application to the paper structure reduced the tensile and burst strengths. However, rosin coating process improved these strengths. In terms of rosin type, natural resin gave better results than commercial resin.
3. Rosin application and coating processes have no significant effect on the optical properties of the photocopy papers.
4. As a result of this study, evaluation of the rosin produced from maritime pine grown in Turkey will contribute the national economy and photocopy papers properties.

5. REFERENCES

- [1]. G. A. Smook, Handbook for Pulp and Paper Technologists, 2nd Edition, Angus Wilde Publications, Vancouver, 1992.
- [2]. A. Yakut, Review of new paper production from recycled used paper, Tesisat Mühendisliği Dergisi, 127: 68-75, 2002.
- [3]. T. Kuusisto, Improving surface sizing operations for an educational paper machine, Bachelor's Thesis, Jyväskylän Ammattikorkeakoulu, JAMK University of Applied Science, 2014.
- [4]. J. P. Casey, Pulp and Paper Chemistry and Chemical Technology, Second Edition, Vol:1, New York, 1960.
- [5]. A. Tutus, S. Gultekin, M. Cicekler, Effects of using starch at size press on physical and optical properties of some packing papers, 1st International Conference on Engineering Technology and Applied Sciences, Afyon Kocatepe University, 111-115, 2016.
- [6]. H. Eroglu, M. Usta, Paper and Board Technology, Karadeniz Technical University Publication, Faculty of Forestry, 2004.
- [7]. A. Tutus, M. Cicekler, S. Gultekin, Increasing water resistance by using resin in corrugated cardboard paper production, 3rd International Non-Wood Forest Products Symposium, 618-623, Kahramanmaraş, 2014.
- [8]. F. Yaltirik, A. Efe, Dendrology Course Book, Istanbul University Faculty of Forestry Publication, Pub. No: 431/3836, İstanbul, 1994.
- [9]. B. Gürboy, Chemical compositions of Pinus pinaster, Journal of Forestry, A(50): 105-111. 2000.
- [10]. A. Karademir, H. Varlibas, M. Cicekler, A study on chemical retention of CaCO₃ on paper production, SDU Faculty of Forestry Journal, 14:48-52, 2013.
- [11]. A. Gencer, H. Eroglu, U. Ayaz, Determination of water absorption (COBB method) values of wheat straw (*Triticum aestivum* L.) paper manufactured by KOH-Air method, Bartın Faculty of Forestry Journal, 11(16): 1-5, 2009.
- [12]. J.W. Swanson, W.K. Ralph, G.M. Robert, The process of sizing, in internal sizing of paper and paperboard, TAPPI, Monograph No:33, pp.193, 1971.